

Maiduguri Flood Disaster Online Media Content: A Gender Framing Analysis

By

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Abstract

This study analyses online media (newspapers and social media) gender framing of the 2024 Maiduguri flood disaster. The objectives of the study are to: identify gendered frames in headlines and article text (videos/images); analyse frames contents in the selected online newspapers and social media; and examine the implication of the gendered frames on the news stories concerning the Maiduguri flood. Anchored in framing theory, the study analyses 61 news items published between 8th and 17th September 2024 by the online version of the Daily Trust, Blueprint, and Punch newspapers, and those mainly published on Facebook, YouTube and TikTok. The study uses quantitative content analysis method. Findings show that framing was dominated by the victim/affected frame, with women and children largely portrayed as vulnerable and dependent, while men were more frequently associated with rescue, support, and institutional authority. Frames highlighting women's leadership, decision-making, and agency was largely absent across platforms. Although social media expanded the volume and visual intensity of coverage, it largely reinforces existing gender stereotypes. The study recommends the adoption of gender-sensitive and inclusive framing practices in both mainstream and digital media especially during disaster such as flood.

Keywords: Gender framing; Maiduguri flood; Disaster reporting; Online newspapers; social media; Framing theory

Introduction

In times of crises, especially flood disasters, the public look up to the media for timely and relevant information because natural disaster like flood has significant but negative effects on people. Thus, natural disaster affects lives, disrupt economies and ecosystems globally, with flood as the most devastating type of disaster (Obaidat *et al.* 2025). This applies to the 2024 flood disaster in Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria. The city became susceptible to flooding in Maiduguri due to its low topography, and its close proximity to the river *Ngadda*. This geographical condition contributes to water accumulation during periods of heavy rainfall. Inadequate or blocked drainage also exacerbate water logging. The flood that destroyed homes and lives in Maiduguri in September 2024 is considered to be the worst ever recorded in the history of floods in the city.

The effect of the flood was felt in most part of Maiduguri metropolis places like popular post office area, Borno Radio and Television station (it was submerged because it is situated along the tributaries of river *Ngadda*)

Maiduguri Monday market to Bulabulin ward, Gwange ward to Gwange Cemetery which flood to the University of Maiduguri Teaching Hospital back to the Government House and Fori ward. With these places mentioned journalists and residents in these areas were also overwhelmed and this could have impact on their perception of the flood disaster.

Public's perception of this type of disaster is influenced by the way the mainstream online and social media platforms capture such incidents. The use of videos and images during disaster and crises evoke strong emotional reaction from people, as it can amplify fear or empathy. Research has shown that, visual coverage often employs human interest frames (Obaidat et al, 2025) with recurring themes portraying victims as passive and reinforcing stereotypes.

The study by Imran et al. (2015) highlights that social media platforms such as X (formerly Twitter) and Instagram enable the rapid dissemination of disaster-related information, supporting situational analysis and damage assessment through both imagery and textual messages. However, as Ngunyen et al, (2017) explain the fear is the misinformation and sensational visual and this remains an issue of concern. As any mishandle information could make people scared and unsure of surviving the flood. Visual framing of news content on flood and any other disaster help shape audience interpretation faster than text because images are processed faster and evoke stronger emotional responses. However, it is important to note that visual images work alongside words and phrases to reinforce particular frames (Psychology & Media, 2025).

More so, news stories are always reported from a specific angle or perspective and that is when media framing takes place during presentation. 'Carefully chosen words, symbols and emphasis to influence how audience interpret events' (Psychology & Media, 2025), eventually give the audience the frame within which the interpretation and understanding takes place in the minds of the audience.

Therefore, this study addresses visual and textual gender framing of news contents in relation to the flood disaster in Maiduguri in the online versions of the mainstream news media – newspapers - and social media news.

The objectives are to:

- i. identify gendered frames in headlines and article text (videos/images)
- ii. analyse framing patterns in selected online newspapers and social media platforms
- iii. examine the implication of the gendered frames on contents on the 2024 Maiduguri flood.

Literature Review

Women in the media are portrayed differently from men across all the media platforms in terms of constructing narratives that are centered around authority, competence and emotions. As Sabharwal (2025) posits, this approach could promote gap gendered framing in media. Women and men in different works of life are framed differently around specific issues in a pattern that is embedded in patriarchal beliefs. The framing process across media organisations are actualised through journalistic routines such as editorial policies, institutional dynamics and ideological currents (Aljalabaneh, 2025). These are some of the factors that affects the framing of issues around gender, gender roles and representations of individuals in roles thought to belong more to males than females by journalists.

The digital era has pushed for transformation in journalism where the mainstream media has to diversified to meet audience information needs. The adaption of social media platforms is not restricted to the mainstream media who wants to diversify but individuals have also become involved part of news gathering, production and distribution real time. These individuals now play the role of citizen journalists using hashtags# when reporting breaking news including the Maiduguri, 2024 flood disaster.

Gendered frames in headlines and News article

Headlines are the first part of a news article that attracts the reader's attention to a news story or make the audience pay attention to the moment a newscaster reads the news bulletin. Research has consistently demonstrated that gender is a salient axis along which framing operates and this influences how men and women are represented in headlines and narratives in articles. As Chowdhury (2025) argues in his study, 'Examining the Role of Headlines in News Framing', headlines operate as 'self-contained frames that can influence news reception, reader engagement and even shape political discourse.' Therefore, headlines can summarily give a picture of what the narrative in a news story is all about and influence the reader's perception about the article. Chowdhury, further assert that not only does gendered framing reflect social realities to the reader/audience it actively reproduces power relations, stereotypes, and normative assumptions about gender roles in the society. This is placing men as leaders, in positions of authority and women as caregivers or supporters in the society. This position is corroborated by other scholars who concur to the assertion that women are passive subjects or symbolic figures, whereas men are active agents, a these reinforce unequal power relations (Chen, Zhai & Su, 2024; Dragas, 2012).

Given the importance of headlines in the place of news stories as an angle which draws the attention of the reader to skim through the information, its role in framing becomes significant because headlines are carefully crafted and the framing elements used in crafting news headlines could reinforce stereotypes. As argued by Chowdhury (2025), headlines play decisive role and decide if a reader will want to read the news piece or not because headlines give an overview of the news.

Nature of Framing in Media

Mainstream newspaper framing operates within institutional settings, where journalists and editors construct frames through professional routines such as gatekeeping, editorial oversight, and adherence to norms of balance, objectivity, and verification. Consequently, content frames are generally coherent, intentional, and relatively stable. (Tandoc, 2013). Meanwhile, social media news framing, in contrast, is decentralized and network-driven. Frames are shaped not only by journalists but also by algorithms, influencers, ordinary users, and online communities, this results in more fragmented and rapidly evolving interpretations driven by interaction, virality, and engagement rather than editorial control (Arugute, Calvo & Ventura, 2022; Lopez-Rabadan, 2022).

Accordingly, framing practices are expected to differ across media systems. In mainstream news organizations, framing is shaped by institutional rules, professional routines, and editorial oversight, which guide and regulate the production of news and result in more coherent and controlled frames. In contrast, social media operates within a participatory and decentralized communication environment in which citizens frequently share breaking or trending information without necessarily recognizing the framing embedded in such content or its potential influence on public perception. As Obaidat et al., (2025) argue, this context heightens the ethical responsibility of both mainstream and digital news outlets (social media) to prioritize accurate, balanced, and reality-based representations, given the powerful role of media framing in shaping how audiences interpret and understand social realities.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the Framing Theory, originally developed by sociologist Erving Goffman in his seminal work, *Frame Analysis: An Essay on the Organization of Experience* (1974). Framing theory explains how individuals and audiences interpret events and social realities based on how information is presented to them rather than the information itself. Goffman posits that the meaning people attach to events is shaped by interpretive frameworks, known as *frames*, which guide perception, understanding, and reaction to social occurrences.

According to Goffman, frames are mental structures that allow individuals to locate, perceive, identify, and label occurrences within their life space. In media contexts, frames influence how news consumers process information by emphasizing certain aspects of reality while downplaying or excluding others. Thus, the same event can generate different interpretations depending on the frame of presentation. This makes framing particularly significant in news reporting and digital communication, where language, images, headlines, and narrative emphasis shape public understanding of events.

Goffman further identifies primary frameworks as the basic interpretive structures people use to make sense of events. These primary frameworks are classified into natural frameworks and social frameworks. Natural frameworks interpret events as physical or environmental occurrences that are not directly caused by human intention, such as natural disasters like floods. Social frameworks, on the other hand, interpret events as the outcome of human actions, intentions, power relations, and social structures.

In media coverage of disasters, such as flood, both frameworks often operate simultaneously. Floods may be framed as natural phenomena caused by heavy rainfall or climate conditions but media narratives may also apply social frameworks by emphasizing human responsibility, government response, social vulnerability, and inequality. These social interpretations become especially important when news stories highlight how disasters affect different social groups, including men and women, differently.

Framing theory is particularly relevant to this study because media frames play a crucial role in shaping gender representations during crisis situations. Gender framing refers to the how media narratives portray men and women, assign roles, depict vulnerability, agency, and responsibility, and reinforce or challenge existing gender stereotypes. Through selective emphasis, mainstream news media and social media platforms may frame women primarily as victims, caregivers, or dependents, while men may be framed as rescuers, decision-makers, or protectors. Such framing influences public perception of gender roles during disasters and may affect policy responses and humanitarian interventions.

In addition, framing theory helps explain the differences between traditional news media and social media content. Mainstream media often rely on professional journalistic routines, institutional norms, and editorial gatekeeping, which can result in standardized or dominant frames. Social media, however, allows for user-generated content (UGC), personal narratives, images, and alternative perspectives, which may challenge, reinforce, or diversify dominant frames in mainstream media. There are little studies on Nigerian flood that adequately addressed the issue of gender framing as most studies do not examine how women and men are represented differently on flood but coverage on the flood is on volume of flood, sources of news story and causes of the flood (Ajaero & Nwachukwu, 2020). In another study on flood in Nigeria, it was on how floods are reported and not how gendered realities are represented (Ejem & Ben-Enukora, 2025).

By applying framing theory, this study examines how the Maiduguri flood crisis is framed in both the mainstream media and social media, with particular attention to gender representation. The theory provides a useful lens for analyzing how media texts construct meaning, highlight gendered experiences of the flood, and shape audience understanding of vulnerability, responsibility, and resilience during the crisis. Consequently, framing theory offers a strong theoretical foundation for comparing gender framing across media platforms and understanding the broader social implications of disaster reporting in Nigeria.

Methodology

This study content analysed mainstream newspaper news and social media post TikTok, YouTube and Facebook. Data was collected to reflect the pre- and post-food periods that is two days before, during and after the flood. This culminated in the analysis of news and social media post between September 8th – 17th 2024, this covered ten days. The food was an episodic event and it lasted for few days before the water receded. A total of 61 news

stories and videos were analysed in the study from mainstream and social media outlets. The online search words used for retrieving the online news content are: - “flood victim”, “Maiduguri floods”, “women and flood”, and hashtags# “flood”, “Maiduguri floods”. The census of all news items found from the online search was analysed in view of the small numbers of articles and posts available at the time of the search. The contents were retrieved in the online versions *Daily Trust*, *Blueprint* and *Punch newspapers*. The study also considered news contents published by *BBC English*, *News Central* and *TVC* correspondents on other media platforms like the YouTube.

The unit of analyses for this study included headlines, lead stories, news features, special reports, pictures, short video on tik Tok, YouTube and Facebook.

The content categories for the study include: - Care giver, victim/affected, support, protector, leader, decision-maker, and were coded using a coding sheet based on the following

Conceptualisation

- i. Caregiving was coded as stories that shows women as taking care of individuals or households affected during the flood.
- ii. Victim/affected: - Coverage of the flood which shows women as more affected and looking helpless or losing items while fleeing from flood affected areas.
- iii. Support: - This refers to news stories or social media posts about support from individuals, groups, philanthropists, government and its agencies, like National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA) and State Emergency Management Agency (SEMA). The support could also be in identifying with the people through visits by politicians and government officials.
- iv. Protector: - These include stories and posts that shows women giving shelter to people affected during the flood or saving individuals from being drowning in the flood.
- v. Leader: - This refers to news coverage and social media posts which shows women taking the lead to direct people to safety
- vi. Decision-maker: - This refers to a news coverage showing a woman in active position of authority, independently or jointly sharing responsibility to make immediate decision on the flood, i.e.: seeking medical care, evacuation, contacting emergency services or arranging transportation.
- vii. Others: news stories, feature news or editorials which do not fall under this category.

Findings

The below table is on the frequency with which the news stories were covered by the online newspapers and other social media handles such as the Facebook, YouTube and TikTok. In the table below, *Blueprint* had a highest in news coverage of the Maiduguri flood of September 10th and the subsequent days after the flood. From the data gathered *Daily Trust* is with the least of news stories covered on the flood issues. While the social media platforms of Facebook and TikTok had 14 video clips each which are news content form *BBC*, *TVC* and *News Central* coverage.

Table 1: Frequency of Content on Maiduguri flood

Newspapers/Social Media Platforms	Frequency
<i>Daily Trust</i>	8 (13.1%)
<i>Blueprint</i>	18 (29.5%)
<i>The Punch</i>	13 (21.3%)
<i>TVC</i>	8 (13.1%)
<i>BBC</i>	5 (8.2%)

<i>News Central</i>	9 (14.7)
<i>Total</i>	61 (100%)

Table 2: Content categories in the online media content

Newspapers and Social Media Platforms	Content Categories Covered							
	<i>Caregiving</i>	<i>Victim/affected</i>	<i>Support</i>	<i>Protection</i>	<i>Leadership</i>	<i>Decision making</i>	<i>Others</i>	<i>Total</i>
<i>Daily Trust</i>	-	1	-	2	-	-	5	8
<i>Blue print</i>	-	2	10		-	-	6	18
<i>The Punch</i>	-	2	6	2	-	-	3	13
<i>TVC</i>	-	3	2			1	2	8
<i>BBC</i>		3	2			-		5
<i>News Central</i>	1	3	4			-	1	9
<i>Total</i>	1	14	24	4		-	18	61

Table 2 present findings on content categories found in the online newspapers and social media platforms. These news stories are for the space of ten days from 8th of September, 2024 to 17th September,2024. The content did not represent all content categories, the roles of decision making, and caregiving roles which women are known for featured only once in *News Central's* report. All the online newspapers were equally silent on this role. Women and their children were mostly captured as the “most affected” and “helpless” in reflections on the role that society saddles them with - nurturing and caring for younger family members. The leadership content category also featured once in a special report by the *TVC* where the Director General of NEMA Zubaida Umar, presented humanitarian aid assistance and spoke on how her agency is planning to augment the effort of the state government and other stakeholders’ support to persons affected by the food.

Table 3 presents data on genre covered and framed in *Daily Trust*, *Blueprint* and *Punch* online newspapers. News stories represent the highest coverage of 30 occurrences. The newspapers assigned more prominence to coverage of the food and support provided by individuals, groups, Non-Governmental Organisations, federal and state governments and relief agencies. Social media platforms mostly comprised videos with short narratives and sounds of gushing waters. Only the *BBC*, *News Central* and *TVC's* clips were covered with a detailed explanations of events during and after the flood. These platforms served as conveyors of visual content on the floods. Most of the pictorial presentation showed women in clusters with their children and wards on the streets, with the few in the camp where they sought shelter. One of the women interviewed by the *BBC* said, “*I thought I will die with my children*”, her comment showed how helpless she was in the midst of the chaos that ensued during the flood. Another woman lost her home and livelihood. While a woman had to pay extra to go back to where she used to live before the flood to rescue her domestic animals. The story items under the opinion/letters to the editor were mostly on the call to government and other stakeholders to support the victims of Maiduguri flood.

The special report narrated the situation of the affected persons who needed support and the effort made by the federal and state government through its agencies NEMA and SEMA. The special report gave an in-depth analysis of the situation on ground during and after the flood waters began to recede. The *BBC* in its special report, featured the woman who lost her home to give her a voice and a platform to be heard and seen.

Table 3: The Genre of Content used for Maiduguri flood

Newspapers and Social Media platforms	Genres of Content						
	News	Features	Opinion/Letters	Editorial	Video /Picture	Special Report	Total
<i>Daily Trust</i>	5		1	1		1	8
<i>Blueprint</i>	14	1	2	1			18
<i>The Punch</i>	11			1	1		13
<i>TVC</i>	7					1	8
<i>BBC</i>	3					2	5
<i>News Central</i>	6				1	2	9
<i>Total</i>	46	1	3	3	2	6	61

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study reveal notable patterns in the coverage and framing of the Maiduguri flood crisis across online newspapers and social media platforms, with clear implications for gender representation in disaster reporting.

Frequency of Flood Framed by Media: The analysis of frequency of coverage indicated that *Blueprint* newspaper devoted the highest level of attention to the flood incident among the selected online newspapers, accounting for nearly one-quarter of all censused stories. This suggested a stronger editorial focus on the flood crisis by *Blueprint* compared to *Daily Trust* and *The Punch*. Furthermore, the *Blueprint* reporter lives in Bulumkutu area of Maiduguri, which was not affected by the flood this gave him the leverage to cover most part of the places affected and gave the reporter the opportunity to cover the development of the events. *Daily Trust* recorded the lowest coverage, which may indicate limited prioritisation of the disaster within its online news agenda. Differences in frequency across newspapers reflect editorial decisions and gatekeeping practices that shape public awareness of humanitarian crises.

Social media platforms particularly Facebook and TikTok also recorded substantial levels of coverage, matching or exceeding some mainstream news outlets. This finding underscores the growing role of social media as an alternative space for disaster communication, especially through audiovisual content. The prominence of social media aligns with the immediacy and participatory nature of these platforms, where users can share real-time visuals and narratives outside conventional journalistic routines.

Gender-Related Frames in Flood Contents in the Media

The study showed a strong dominance of the victim/affected frame, which accounted for the highest number of portrayals across all platforms. Women and children were most frequently depicted as victims of the flood, often shown as displaced, stranded, or dependent on humanitarian aid. This finding is consistent with previous observations in disaster reporting where women are commonly framed as passive sufferers rather than active agents.

The support frame, which highlights relief efforts by government agencies, security forces, and humanitarian organisations, was also prominent, particularly in mainstream newspapers and TikTok content. However, these support narratives largely centered on institutional actors such as the military, emergency agencies, and government officials who were predominantly male. This framing reinforces gendered power relations by associating men with authority, rescue, and control, while women remain positioned as recipients of assistance.

Notably, frames related to leadership, protection, and decision-making were either minimally represented or completely absent. The near-absence of women in leadership and decision-making roles suggests a narrow and stereotypical construction of gender roles in flood coverage. Even in instances where women played visible roles within affected communities, these contributions were largely excluded from media narratives. This omission reflects the operation of social frames that normalise male leadership and marginalise women's agency during crises.

Caregiving frame and media silence

One of the most striking findings is the limited representation of the caregiving role, despite its cultural association with women. While TikTok and some social media content briefly depicted women caring for children and dependents, online newspapers were largely silent on this frame. This absence may indicate a preference for dramatic and event-driven narratives such as rescue operations and destruction over everyday survival practices that sustain displaced families. As a result, women's invisible labour during disasters remains underreported and undervalued.

Genre and mode of storytelling

This revealed that mainstream newspapers relied heavily on straight news reporting, with minimal use of features, editorials, or in-depth analyses. This limited contextual engagement with gendered experiences of the flood, as straight news formats often prioritise immediacy over interpretation. In contrast, social media platforms overwhelmingly used videos and images, which visually reinforced gendered frames.

Meanwhile, visual representations across platforms consistently showed women in clusters with children, either on the streets or in displacement camps. These recurring images contributed to the symbolic framing of women as vulnerable and dependent, while men were more frequently associated with action-oriented visuals such as rescue missions and logistics. Although some broadcast media clips shared on social media provided more detailed explanations, the dominant visual narrative remained gender-stereotypical.

Implications for Gender Framing and Media Practice

Overall, the findings demonstrate that both mainstream news media and social media platforms reproduced gendered frames that emphasise women's vulnerability while minimising their agency, leadership, and decision-making capacities during the Maiduguri flood crisis. Social media expanded the volume and immediacy of coverage, but failed to substantially challenge dominant gender frames in mainstream journalism. Instead, it amplified them through repetitive visuals and emotionally charged narratives.

From a framing theory perspective, these patterns show how media selectively emphasised certain aspects of the flood victimhood, rescue, and institutional response while excluding alternative frames that could highlight women's resilience, leadership, and participation in recovery efforts. Such framing has broader social implications, as it shapes public perception of gender roles during disasters and may influence policy priorities and humanitarian responses.

Conclusion

This study examined the framing of gender on the 2024 Maiduguri flood crisis through a comparative analysis of selected online newspapers and social media platforms. The findings demonstrate that while both mainstream news media and social media played significant roles in reporting the flood, their coverage largely reproduced gendered and stereotypical frames. Women were predominantly portrayed as victims and affected persons, often visually represented alongside children in displacement settings, while men were more frequently associated with rescue operations, institutional authority, and support activities.

The dominance of the victim/affected frame across platforms suggested that disaster reporting continues to emphasise vulnerability over agency, in relation to women. Although social media expanded the volume and immediacy of coverage through videos and images, it failed to substantially disrupt dominant gender narratives in mainstream journalism. Instead, social media amplified these frames through repetitive visuals that reinforced women's dependence and marginalised their leadership, decision-making, and resilience during the crisis.

Furthermore, limited use of diverse genres such as features, editorials, and special reports constrained deeper engagement with the gendered dimensions of the flood. The absence of women in leadership, protection, and decision-making frames reflected broader structural biases in media representations and underscores the need for more inclusive and balanced disaster narratives. Overall, the study concluded that media framing of the 2024 Maiduguri flood crisis, across both mainstream and digital platforms, inadequately captured women's multifaceted roles and experiences, thereby shaping public perception in ways that reinforce existing gender inequalities.

Recommendations

Media organisations should consciously adopt gender-sensitive frameworks in disaster reporting. Journalists and content creators should move beyond victim-centered narratives to highlight women's agency, resilience, leadership, and participation in response and recovery efforts.

News media should deliberately incorporate frames related to decision-making, protection, leadership, and community organisation, especially as they relate to women. This would provide a more balanced and accurate representation of gender roles during crises. Social media platforms and users should be encouraged to present visuals that reflect diverse gender experiences rather than reinforcing stereotypes. Visual narratives should balance scenes of vulnerability with those of agency, cooperation, and recovery.

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